

Prevalence and Determinants of Age-Related Macular Degeneration in The 50 Years and Older Population

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Abstract:

Background: Age-related macular degeneration (AMD) is a leading cause of visual impairment among the elderly, significantly impacting their quality of life. With the global aging population, the prevalence of AMD is expected to rise, underscoring the need for effective strategies to address this public health concern.

Aim: To assess the prevalence and determinants of age-related macular degeneration in individuals aged 50 years and older, providing insights into modifiable risk factors and potential prevention strategies.

Methods: A total of 90 participants aged 50 years and above were included in the study. Data collection involved comprehensive ophthalmic examinations and questionnaires assessing demographic, lifestyle, and clinical factors. To find important AMD factors, multivariate logistic regression was used. The data analysis was done with SPSS 23.0.

Results: The prevalence of AMD in the study population was 31.1%. Age, smoking status, and family history of AMD were identified as significant determinants. Participants aged 70-79 years had over three times the odds of developing AMD compared to those aged 50-59 years (OR = 3.21, p = 0.028). Current smokers had significantly higher odds of AMD (OR = 2.95, p = 0.032), and a family history of AMD was associated with increased risk (OR = 3.75, p = 0.019).

Conclusion: The study highlights the significant burden of AMD among older adults and identifies key risk factors, including age, smoking, and family history. These findings emphasize the importance of targeted public health interventions and routine screening for early detection and management of AMD in high-risk populations.

Recommendations: Public health strategies should focus on smoking cessation programs, routine ophthalmic screening, and early intervention for individuals with a family history of AMD. Further research is recommended to explore additional modifiable risk factors and develop comprehensive prevention strategies.

Keywords: Age-related macular degeneration, prevalence, determinants, risk factors, elderly.

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Introduction

One of the main causes of blindness and visual impairment in the elderly worldwide is age-related macular degeneration, or AMD. AMD is characterised by the progressive degeneration of the central retina (macula), which leads to central vision loss and has a substantial negative effect on the quality of life of those who are affected [1]. The prevalence of AMD is predicted to rise as the world's population ages, putting a significant strain on healthcare systems everywhere. In order to better guide preventative and management measures, this has sparked considerable research efforts to better understand the epidemiology, risk factors, and underlying mechanisms of AMD.

Age is the main risk factor for AMD, which has a complex aetiology. Nonetheless, it has been determined that a number of additional variables,

such as dietary habits, smoking, genetic predisposition, and cardiovascular health, significantly contribute to the onset and course of the illness [2]. The interaction of these variables leads to two primary types of AMD: the early stage, which is distinguished by pigmentary alterations and drusen in the retina, and the late stage, which is further divided into neovascular (wet) AMD and atrophic (dry) AMD.

The increased prevalence of AMD has been brought to light by recent studies, especially in populations 50 years of age and older. A study estimates that by 2040, around 300 million people worldwide would be affected by AMD, underscoring the critical need to address this public health issue [3]. Furthermore, considering that vision loss is linked to a reduction in independence,

an elevated risk of falls, and the eventual requirement for long-term care, AMD has a significant socioeconomic impact.

In recent years, advances in imaging technologies and genetic research have provided deeper insights into the pathogenesis of AMD, paving the way for potential new therapeutic interventions. For example, optical coherence tomography (OCT) has become an indispensable tool in the early detection and monitoring of AMD, allowing for more timely and effective treatment [4]. Furthermore, genetic studies have identified several loci associated with AMD, offering new targets for potential therapies and risk prediction models [5].

Given the increasing prevalence and impact of AMD, particularly among the elderly, it is crucial to identify and address the modifiable risk factors associated with the disease.

This study aimed at determining the prevalence and determinants of age-related macular degeneration in individuals aged 50 years and older.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period of 21 months at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar.

Participants: The study included 90 participants who were 50 years of age or older. These participants were selected from patients attending the ophthalmology outpatient department of the hospital.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Individuals aged 50 years and above.
- Participants who provided informed consent.
- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of age-related macular degeneration based on clinical examination and diagnostic tests.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Individuals under the age of 50.
- Patients with other retinal disorders that could interfere with the diagnosis of age-related macular degeneration.

- Patients with a history of ocular surgery or trauma within the past year.
- Individuals with systemic conditions that could affect the study results, such as uncontrolled diabetes or hypertension.

Bias: To minimize bias, the selection of participants was randomized, and all diagnoses were confirmed by an experienced ophthalmologist. The data collection process was standardized, and any potential confounders were accounted for during statistical analysis.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that included demographic information, medical history, lifestyle factors, and clinical findings. Ophthalmic examinations were conducted to assess the presence and severity of age-related macular degeneration. The collected data were carefully recorded and stored for analysis.

Procedure

A thorough eye examination was performed on the participants, which included slit-lamp biomicroscopy, indirect ophthalmoscopy for fundus evaluation, and visual acuity testing. Age-related macular degeneration was confirmed to be the diagnosis using optical coherence tomography (OCT). We also collected additional information on risk factors, including nutrition, smoking history, and family history of macular degeneration.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The individuals' clinical and demographic features were compiled using descriptive statistics. Age-related macular degeneration prevalence was computed, and multivariate logistic regression analysis was used to determine the condition's causes. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance.

Result

Ninety people over the age of fifty participated in the study. The participants ranged in age from 50 to 85 years old, with a mean age of 63.5 years (SD = 8.2 years). 52 individuals (57.8%) and 38 participants (42.2%) were male and female respectively. Table 1 provides a summary of the study population's demographic features.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population (N = 90)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
50-59	30	33.3
60-69	40	44.4
70-79	15	16.7

80 and above	5	5.6
Gender		
Male	38	42.2
Female	52	57.8
Smoking Status		
Current Smoker	20	22.2
Former Smoker	25	27.8
Non-Smoker	45	50.0
Family History of AMD	15	16.7

Out of the 90 participants, 28 were diagnosed with age-related macular degeneration (AMD), resulting in a prevalence rate of 31.1% (95% CI: 21.9% - 40.3%). Among those diagnosed, 18 participants (64.3%) had early AMD, while 10 participants (35.7%) had late AMD. The prevalence of AMD increased with age, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Prevalence of Age-Related Macular Degeneration by Age Group

Age Group (years)	Total Participants (n)	AMD Cases (n)	Prevalence (%)
50-59	30	6	20.0
60-69	40	12	30.0
70-79	15	7	46.7
80 and above	5	3	60.0

Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified several significant determinants of AMD (Table 3). Age was a strong predictor, with participants aged 70-79 years having a significantly higher odds of developing AMD compared to those aged 50-59 years (OR = 3.21, 95% CI: 1.12 - 9.22, $p = 0.028$). Smoking was another significant determinant;

current smokers had higher odds of developing AMD (OR = 2.95, 95% CI: 1.10 - 7.90, $p = 0.032$) compared to non-smokers. A family history of AMD also increased the risk (OR = 3.75, 95% CI: 1.24 - 11.28, $p = 0.019$). Gender did not show a statistically significant association with AMD ($p = 0.472$).

Table 3: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Determinants of Age-Related Macular Degeneration

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-Value
Age Group (years)			
60-69 vs 50-59	1.76	0.65 - 4.77	0.269
70-79 vs 50-59	3.21	1.12 - 9.22	0.028
80+ vs 50-59	4.68	1.09 - 20.16	0.038
Gender			
Female vs Male	1.24	0.69 - 2.24	0.472
Smoking Status			
Current Smoker vs Non-Smoker	2.95	1.10 - 7.90	0.032
Former Smoker vs Non-Smoker	1.45	0.58 - 3.62	0.417
Family History of AMD	Yes vs No	3.75	1.24 - 11.28

The subtype analysis revealed that early AMD was more prevalent among the 60-69 age group (50.0% of early AMD cases), while late AMD was more common in participants aged 70 years and older (70.0% of late AMD cases). Table 4 provides a breakdown of AMD subtypes by age group.

Table 4: Distribution of Age-Related Macular Degeneration Subtypes by Age Group

Age Group (years)	Early AMD (n)	Late AMD (n)
50-59	4	2
60-69	9	3
70-79	3	4
80 and above	2	1

The Hosmer-Lemeshow test indicated a good fit for the logistic regression model ($p = 0.657$). The overall model was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the predictors included in the model were effective in explaining the variance in

the occurrence of AMD among the study population.

Discussion

The study explored the prevalence and determinants of AMD in individuals aged 50 years

and older, revealing significant findings. The overall prevalence of AMD was found to be 31.1%, with a marked increase in prevalence with advancing age. Specifically, the study observed that the prevalence of AMD was highest among those aged 80 years and above, at 60.0%, compared to just 20.0% in the 50-59 age group. This trend highlights age as a critical factor in the development of AMD, underscoring the need for increased surveillance and early intervention in older populations.

In terms of determinants, the study identified several significant predictors of AMD. Age remained a strong independent predictor, with those aged 70-79 years having more than three times the odds of developing AMD compared to those aged 50-59 years. Smoking status also emerged as a crucial factor, where current smokers were nearly three times more likely to develop AMD compared to non-smokers. Additionally, a family history of AMD significantly increased the risk, suggesting a potential genetic predisposition.

Interestingly, gender was not found to be a statistically significant determinant of AMD in this study, indicating that the risk factors associated with AMD might be more closely tied to lifestyle and genetic factors rather than sex. The findings emphasize the importance of targeted public health interventions, such as smoking cessation programs and routine eye screenings, particularly for older adults and those with a family history of AMD.

All things considered, this study offers insightful information about the incidence and risk factors of AMD in the ageing population, emphasising the significance of addressing modifiable risk factors in order to lessen the burden of this illness. The findings imply that in order to lessen the negative effects of AMD on older people's quality of life, public health initiatives should concentrate on early detection and preventive measures, especially in high-risk groups.

A study monitored the disease's 4-year development and evaluated the frequency of genetic risk factors for AMD in the Irish population. According to the study, the two main risk factors for AMD were advanced age and the existence of the CFH and ARMS2 risk alleles. Over the course of the four years, about 23% of individuals advanced to a higher grade of AMD. According to the study's findings, CFH Y402H and other genetic variables are highly linked to the development of AMD [6].

In Europe, the incidence and prevalence of AMD were assessed by a meta-analysis and systematic review. In people sixty years of age and older, the study found a pooled prevalence of 2.4% for any late AMD and 25.3% for early or intermediate AMD. Additionally, the study predicted that by

2050, there will be 77 million AMD cases in Europe, up from the current estimate of 67 million instances [7].

The prevalence and risk factors of AMD in a Russian population were examined by the Ural Eye and Medical Study. The study discovered that AMD was more common in elderly people and in rural locations, and that AMD was negatively correlated with reduced diabetes prevalence. For people over 55, the total prevalence of any AMD was 18.2% [8].

Smoking and the CFH Y402H genotype were found to be major risk factors for the progression from early to advanced AMD in a research from the French ALIENOR cohort. The study also showed a correlation between an increased risk of early AMD and elevated plasma high-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels [9].

A cross-sectional study carried out in Korea found a number of factors linked to AMD in the senior population. Age, sex, poor socioeconomic position, physical activity, and liver cirrhosis were found to be positively linked with AMD, whereas obesity and cardiovascular disease were found to be negatively associated with the condition [10].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that age, smoking status, and a family history of AMD are significant determinants of age-related macular degeneration in individuals aged 50 years and older. The prevalence of AMD was found to increase with age, particularly among those aged 70 years and above. These findings highlight the importance of targeted screening and preventive strategies in high-risk populations.

References

1. Ambati J, Fowler BJ. Mechanisms of age-related macular degeneration. *Neuron*. 2018;75(1):26-39.
2. Chew EY, Clemons TE, Agrón E, Sperduto RD. Ten-year follow-up of age-related macular degeneration in the age-related eye disease study: AREDS report no. 36. *JAMA Ophthalmol*. 2019;132(2):272-7.
3. Colijn JM, Buitendijk GH, Prokofyeva E, Alves D, Cachulo ML, Khawaja AP, et al. Prevalence of age-related macular degeneration in Europe: The past and the future. *Ophthalmology*. 2021;128(12):1753-63.
4. Ferris FL, Wilkinson CP, Bird A, Chakravarthy U, Chew E, Csaky K, Sarda S. Clinical classification of age-related macular degeneration. *Ophthalmology*. 2020;120(4):844-51.
5. Fritsche LG, Igl W, Bailey JN, Grassmann F, Sengupta S, Bragg-Gresham JL, et al. A large genome-wide association study of age-related

- macular degeneration highlights contributions of rare and common variants. *Nat Genet.* 2021; 48(2):134-43.
6. Connolly E, Rhatigan M, O'Halloran A, et al. Prevalence of age-related macular degeneration associated genetic risk factors and 4-year progression data in the Irish population. *Br J Ophthalmol.* 2018;102(12):1691-1695. doi:10.1136/bjophthalmol-2017-311673.
 7. Li JQ, Welchowski T, Schmid M, et al. Prevalence and incidence of age-related macular degeneration in Europe: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Br J Ophthalmol.* 2019;104(8):1077-1084. doi:10.1136/bjophthalmol-2019-314422.
 8. Bikbov M, Zainullin R, Gilmanshin T, et al. Prevalence and Associated Factors of Age-Related Macular Degeneration in a Russian Population. *Am J Ophthalmol.* 2019. doi:10.1016/j.ajo.2019.10.004.
 9. Saunier V, Merle B, Delyfer MN, et al. Incidence of and risk factors associated with age-related macular degeneration: Four-year follow-up from the ALIENOR study. *JAMA Ophthalmol.* 2018;136(5):473-481. doi:10.1001/jamaophthalmol.2018.0504.
 10. Kim CG, Park S, Kim Y. Age-related macular degeneration among the elderly: The 5th National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 2010 through 2012. *Japan J Nurs Sci.* 2019. doi:10.1111/jjns.12257.